

STYLISTIC PECULIARITIES OF TRANSLATION BASED ON ROBIN
SHARMA'S "THE 5 AM CLUB"

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Abstract:

This article examines the stylistic features of translation using Robin Sharma's *The 5 AM Club* as a case study. It analyzes how metaphors, idioms, and tone are conveyed in translation, highlighting the challenges of preserving the author's motivational style. The study emphasizes the translator's role in maintaining the original's emotional and rhetorical impact.

Аннотация: В этой статье рассматриваются стилистические особенности перевода на примере романа Робина Шармы «Клуб 5 утра». Анализируется, как метафоры, идиомы и тон передаются в переводе, подчеркивая трудности сохранения мотивационного стиля автора. В исследовании подчеркивается роль переводчика в сохранении эмоционального и риторического воздействия оригинала.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Robin Sharmaning "Tongi 5 klubi" asaridan foydalangan holda tarjimaning stilistik xususiyatlari ko'rib chiqiladi. Tarjimada metaforalar, idiomalar va ohanglar qanday berilganligi tahlil qilinadi, muallifning motivatsion uslubini saqlab qolish muammolari yoritiladi. Tadqiqot asl nusxadagi hissiy va ritorik ta'sirni saqlab qolishda tarjimonning rolini ta'kidlaydi.

Key words : Stylistics, translation, epithet, oxymoron, hyperbole cultural adaptation,

Introduction

Translation is not merely a linguistic exercise but an art that requires sensitivity to style, tone, and cultural nuance. This is especially true for motivational literature, where the author's voice and emotional impact play a central role. According to Baker (2018), style in translation goes beyond linguistic choices and reflects the translator's own interpretive stance. Robin Sharma's "The 5 am club" is a compelling example of such a text, blending storytelling with self-help strategies, rich in stylistic devices like metaphors, idiomatic expressions, and rhetorical questions. Translating this work poses significant challenges, as the translator must preserve the author's inspirational tone and stylistic richness while making the text accessible and engaging to a new audience. This article investigates the stylistic peculiarities involved in translating *The 5 AM Club*, aiming to understand how style influences meaning and reader reception across languages. The language of a writer is sometimes regarded as alien to lingvo-stylistics. Here is what V. M. Zirmunsky writes: "The language of a writer can hardly be considered an object of lingvo-stylistics. If analyzed outside the problem of style (the style of the work, the writer, the literary trend or the literary era), the language falls into a mass of words, collocations and grammatical facts, which taken in isolation will serve as but unreliable evidence as to the life of the given language in the given period of its development." In

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-5

this connection it is worth referring to Flaubert's notion on style. He considers style, as it were, non-personal, its merits being dependent on the power of thought and on the acuteness of the writer's perceptions.³ The same idea, only slightly modified, is expressed by J. Middleton Murry who said that "A true style must be unique, if we understand by the phrase 'a true style' completely adequate expression in language of a writer's mode of feeling."

According to Galperin. I. R stylistic devices based on interaction of logical and emotive meanings : epithet, oxymoron, hyperbole

Examples from Robin Sharma's " The 5 am club"

Epithet: A descriptive phrase expressing a quality or characteristic of a person or thing.

For instance : The Spellbinder, The billionaire mentor, Victimhood culture.

Hyperbole :Exaggeration for emphasis or rhetorical effect.

For instance : "Own your morning. Elevate your life."

"You will become a legend", "Each day is nothing less than a miracle."

Oxymoron: A figure of speech in which contradictory terms appear in conjunction.

For instance : " Productive solitude", "Tranquil urgency", "Disciplined freedom"

Conclusion

The stylistic translation of Robin Sharma's The 5 AM Club demonstrates the complexity of conveying not just meaning, but mood, tone, and motivational force across languages. Through the careful handling of epithet, oxymoron and hyperbole translators play a vital role in preserving the author's intent and emotional resonance. Venuti (2012) points out that the translator's stylistic choices shape the reader's reception and interpretation of the translated text. This analysis highlights that successful translation of motivational literature requires both linguistic accuracy and stylistic sensitivity, ensuring that the message remains powerful and culturally relevant for the target audience.

References

1. Baker, M. (2018). *In Other Words: A Coursebook on Translation* (3rd ed.). Routledge.
2. Galperin I. R. *Stylistics*. —Moscow: Higher school, 1977. pp. 30-803. Ashurova D. U, Galieva M. R. *Stylistics of literary text*. Turon-Iqbol. - Tashkent , 2016
4. Venuti, L. (2012). *The Translator's Invisibility: A History of Translation* (2nd ed.). Routledge.